

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN AMERICAN AND BRITISH ACCENT

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Annotation: This article describes differences between British and American accent. The between British and American accent is the common problem for realize. Also information was given about when the English language appeared

Anotatsiya; Ushbu maqolada Britaniya talaffuzi va Amerika talaffuzi o'rtasidagi farqni tushunish uchun umumiy muammo tasvirlangan. Bundan tashqari ingliz tili qachon paydo bo'lganligi haqida ham ma'lumot berildi.

Key words: American and British accent, linguistic, heritage, lexical, pronunciation

Introduction

English languages, West Germanic language of the Indo-European language family .That is closely related to German and Dutch languages. English originated in England and is the dominant language of the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, Ireland, New Zealand, and various Island nations in the Caribbean sea and The Pacific Ocean. The English language emerged from the fusion of various language, primarily Anglo-Saxon, Old Norse, and Norman French, following the Norman Conquest of England in 1066.

Over time, it evolved through influences from Latin, Greek, other languages, becoming the global-lingua franca due to the British Empire's expansion and later the United States' cultural and economic influence. English is the most studied language in the world and the main language of communication around the world. by the 16-17th centuries, Americans had created their own English language. Both countries England and America actually speak English but there are cultural differences in speaking the language. American and British accents are broad categories that encompass many regional variation within each country. American English accents can vary significantly from region to region, but some general features include rhoticity pronouncing the "r" sound in words like "car" and "park", the cot-caught merger where the vowel in words like "coat" and "caught" are pronounced the same. British English accents also have numerous regional variations, including Received Pronunciation, which is often associated with the South East of England and is traditionally

considered the standard accent in the UK. Features of RP include non-rhoticity not pronouncing “r” sound in words like “car” and “park”, the trap-bath split where the vowels in words like “trap” and “bath” are pronounced differently, and the presence of the FOOT-STRUT split where the vowels words like “foot” and “strut” are pronounced differently.

The Pronunciation of English and British English are different and the phonetic symbols used are slightly different. American English used to use the Webster Noah Phonetic alphabet. The main difference between the phonetic symbols are the same except for a few different ones.

1. Differences in consonants; There are 24 consonants in British English and 25 consonants in American English. They can be divided into two categories; clear consonants and voiced consonants. When consonants are pronounced, airflow exhales from the lungs, passes through the trachea and vocal cords, and is obstructed by a certain vocal organ and comes out from the mouth or nasal cavity. Therefore, in American English, the “r” sound is often pronounced more prominently, especially at the end of the words like “car” or “letter”. In British English, the “r” sound may be less pronounced or even dropped, particularly in certain dialects like Received pronunciation. In American English, the “t” sound is often pronounced more like a flap, especially in the middle of words or between vowels, as in “butter” or “water”. In British English, the “t” sound tends to be more aspirated, especially at the beginning of the words, as in “top” or “tea”.

2. Vocabulary and Idioms; There are some differences in vocabulary and idioms between American and British English. Most words mean the same thing in British and American English. For example, the words “apple” and “chair” refer to the same objects in both versions of English. For the most part, speakers of American English and British won’t have much trouble at all understanding one another when it comes to vocabulary. This is far from the only example, through here are just a few more examples of two different words being used to refer to the same thing;

Truck (US) / Lorry (UK); A large vehicle used for transporting goods.

Apartment (US) / Flat (UK); A set of rooms for living in, typically on one floor of a building.

Elevator (US) / Lift (UK); A platform or compartment that moves vertically to carry people or goods between floors of a building.

Sweater (US) / Jumper (UK); A knitted garment worn on the upper body.

Cookie (US) / Biscuit (UK); A sweet baked food item .

IDIOMS ;

American and British English have numerous differences in idiomatic expressions, reflecting their distinct cultural influences and historical developments .

“Hit the suck” (US) / “Hit the hay” (UK); To go to bed .

“Piece of cake” (US) / “Piece of pudding” (UK); Something very easy to do .

“Hang out” (US) / “Chill out” (UK); To relax or spend time with friends .

“In a pickle” (US) “In a jam” (UK); “In a jam” (UK); In a difficult situation .

“Jump the gun” (US) / “Jump the queue”(UK); To act too soon or before the appropriate time .

3.The changes of a stress position.

In both American and British English stress plays a significant role in pronunciation and meaning.

However there are some general differences in stress patterns between the two accents;

1.Word stress: American English typically places primary stress on the first syllable of longer words and compound nouns (“record”, “contract”)

British English: Often places primary stress on the second syllable of longer words and compound nouns (“record”, “contrast”)

2. Sentence stress:

American English ; Tends to have a more consistent stress pattern, with a relatively even stress distribution across words in a sentence. Furthermore , British English may exhibit more variability in stress patterns within sentences, often influenced by factors such as emphasis and context .

3.Regional Variation:

Diversity within each accent ;

Both American and British accents encompass a wide range of regional variations, each with its own unique features and nuances. From the Southern drawl of the United states to the Scottish brogue of Britain, regional accents add further complexity to the comparison .

Conclusion

In conclusion, while both American and British accent share similarities, they also exhibit notable differences in vowel sounds, consonant pronunciation, and intonation patterns these distinctions reflect the diverse linguistic evolution and cultural influences in each region, contributing to the rich tapestry of English accents worldwide. Generally,

the main stress falls further to the left in British than in American English, with the latter variety accommodating stress more the word edges than the former. Lexical type and origin form categories which are differentially treated in the two dialects .

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